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Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

SALVADOR TAN PELONIA JR

Teacher I Applicant

Division of Northern Samar

Salvadorjrpelonia012@gmail.com

“COLD COMFORT”

My heart leaps with gladness now,
As he whispers love so tender, so true,
With blooms in hand, in shades that I knew.
A smile graces me, my heart feels light,
As he kneels before me, his eyes burning bright.

Tears spill, silent and slow,
Hounding sorrow down his cheeks.
Does he weep for the bruises he left,
Or for the promise he could not keep?

“It’s okay, my love, you’re forgiven,”
He kneels, trembling, head bowed low.
“Don’t be,” I whisper, “I am only me.

I am happier now.
Freezing winds whisper through my bones,
Thank you for the flowers, so bright yet cold,
With candlelight glimmering, silent and gold—
Though today is no celebration of birth.
The white dress wraps me in quiet grace,
A perfect fit for my resting place.
Thank you for the coffin.